

The Effect of Emotional Exhaustion and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at Telkomsel RTPO Work Unit in Sumatera Area

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ABSTRACT

The availability of Telkomsel's BTS (Base Transceiver Station) network of production equipment on Telkomsel services in the Sumatera Area did not achieve the specified target by management for 2 consecutive years, from 2017-2018. The target determined is the percentage value of network availability (the level of performance of production equipment in operating to serve customers) must reach at least 99.1%. This condition shows that the RTPO Work Unit in the Sumatera Area has not been optimal in operating production equipment so the network services are still experiencing disruptions, and also lead to a decrease in revenue. This encourages the researcher to research employee performance in the Telkomsel RTPO Work Unit in Sumatera Area by testing the variables of emotional exhaustion and job satisfaction as factors which affect it. The study was conducted on 84 (eighty-four) employees in the RTPO Work Unit in the Sumatera Area as the population. Path analysis method with SPSS Statistics was implemented, the conclusion showed that emotional exhaustion did not have a significant effect on employee performance, job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance, and emotional exhaustion significantly affects the performance through job satisfaction.

Keywords: RTPO Work Unit, Emotional Exhaustion, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

Telkomsel Sumatera Area consists of 3 regions, namely Sumbagut, Sumbagteng and Sumbagsel. Each of the three regions

has a work unit called RTPO (Radio Transport Power Operation). The RTPO work unit is the frontline in serving customers spread across 152 Regencies and Municipalities in Sumatera. Each RTPO unit must ensure that the existing telecommunications network must operate 24 hours a day (100% network availability) so that customers can communicate voice and data services properly. The RTPO work unit is part of the organization in Telkomsel Sumatera with work locations up to the district level. This work unit deals with technical matters, including aspects of Radio, Transport and Power. The definition of the scope of work Radio in this work unit is responsible for Base Sub System (BSS) devices such as BTS / NodeB / eNodeB, BSC / RNC, Router. The function of this BSS device is as a sender and receiver (transceiver) of communication between mobile stations (mobile phones). The definition of the scope of work Transport in this work unit is to emit Radio Frequency (RF) signals that carry information signals in the form of images (Video) and sound (Audio) from a BTS so that it can be received by the BTS receiver (receiver) in the area covered by the BTS transmitter. Both the scope of work above both radio and transport can't function optimally if without the support of the power supply or the so-called power.

Based on this description, it can be seen that the main focus and responsibility of the RTPO work unit in maintaining

network services are Radio, Transport, and Power. However, the current condition of the RTPO work unit has always been used as an extension of activities both from regional and head office. Matters that are supposed to be technical in the context of responsibility are shifted to non-technical matters which must be carried out due to the distance that must be taken from regional or central in terms of problem solving. Based on the results of initial interviews in January 2019 with some North Sumatra RTPO employees, that the non-technical matters that are demanded are usually related to the negotiation process, the resolution of land disputes where telecommunications equipment is installed, licenses to regional governments, the police and so on. This makes every employee of the RTPO work unit required to be able to do all things that are non-technical without adequate skills because it is not a field under his control.

The high work variance and the amount of responsibility that must be carried out, making employees often experience Exhaustion (mental Exhaustion), so that employees feel they become less focused and difficult to concentrate in undergoing supervision of production equipment. Employees often experience delays in terms of handling problematic production equipment. This has resulted in the performance of RTPO employees not optimal in maintaining network services in their area, not even reaching the target for two years in a row. Emotional Exhaustion is a part of the three dimensions of burn out namely emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and low self-confidence (Maslach, 1993). The service profession, in this case RTPO employees (maintaining communication network services) is basically a job that faces demands and emotional involvement. Daily interactions with superiors, colleagues, and the local community often lead to pressures and challenges that cause emotional tension and can cause stress. Based on the results of interviews with 10 North Sumatra Area RTPO employees, by asking employees'

perceptions of the causes of performance that were not achieved for two years in a row, there was a phenomenon of employee dissatisfaction with the awards given. The increased workload of employees in the RTPO work unit in handling non-technical tasks turned out to be relatively not balanced by a balanced award.

When stress at work is inevitable, psychological and behavioral consequences can occur. The consequences of stressful and demanding work conditions are defined as emotional exhaustion (Freudenberger and Maslach in David Friesen & Prokop, 1988). In Zagladi's research (2004) which showed that emotional exhaustion consisting of workload, rewards, role conflict and family environment had an effect on job satisfaction, the higher the emotional Exhaustion felt by PTS lecturers the lower the job satisfaction achieved. Someone with a high level of job satisfaction shows a positive attitude towards work, someone who is dissatisfied with his job shows a negative attitude towards work (Robbins, 1996). A person's job satisfaction is always associated with performance. Performance (work performance) is the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him (Mangkunegara, 2004). Performance has an important role for the company, if the performance displayed is low, it will cause the company to achieve its objectives to be hampered (Ariani and Riana, 2013). Mathis and Jackson (2009) stated that the factors that influence performance are job satisfaction or dissatisfaction other than the individual itself, work and organizational commitment.

Emotional exhaustion

Emotional exhaustion as a dimension of burnout arises because of excessive stress and difficult to overcome which can lead an individual to a worse situation where apathy, cynicism, frustration, and withdrawal develop (Widiastuti and Kamsih, 2008). Nurjayadi

(2004) said that the decrease in individual work is the impact of negative attitudes and behaviors caused by burnout. In more detail, Maslach and Leiter (in Gunarsa, 2004) revealed that the source or cause of burnout, as an aspect that results in emotional exhaustion, can be traced into 6 aspects namely (1) overwork, (2) lack of control at work, (3) Inadequate or inappropriate system of rewards, (4) Disruption of the community system at work, (5) Loss of justice in the work environment, and (6) value conflicts. In this study, the emotional exhaustion variable is described in 3 dimensions, namely:

1. **Workload;** In the perspective of the organization workload means productivity, whereas in the perspective of the individual workload means limited time and energy. The tight competition requires management to work efficiency. Everyone is required to do many things with limited time and money. As a result, every worker gets a burden that often exceeds their capacity. They have to carry out various kinds of tasks and those tasks are increasingly complex with more demands on quality and quantity due to competition.
2. **Award;** The lack of balance between an extrinsic reward system (salary and benefits) and an intrinsic reward system will weaken the enthusiasm for liking work and ultimately make one feel shackled by routine things that result in decreased commitment and work motivation.
3. **Work Environment;** Tight competition and heavy working hours cause workers to be separated from other workers. The company's work climate that is competitive, individual and prioritizes achievement can cause feelings of discomfort because social relationships become pragmatic and separation from the social environment actually creates a feeling of insecurity for someone who in the end easily triggers conflict. The work environment is considered to be fair if it has three things: trust, openness

and respect. These three aspects are important for maintaining one's involvement in their work.

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is the way a worker feels his job. Job satisfaction is a generalization of attitudes towards work based on aspects of the job. A person's attitude towards his job reflects pleasant and unpleasant experiences in his work as well as his hopes for future experiences (Wexley & Yukl, 2005). Job satisfaction refers to an individual's general attitude towards his job. Someone with a high level of job satisfaction has a positive attitude towards their work; someone who is dissatisfied with his job has a negative attitude towards the job (Robbins, 2002). According to Smith, Kendall, and Hullin over the years, five job dimensions have been identified to present the most important job characteristics in which employees have affective responses. The five dimensions are:

1. **The work itself;** Job satisfaction from the job itself is the main source of satisfaction. Recent research finds job characteristics and job complexity linking between personality and job satisfaction (Judge, Bono, & Locke, 2000). If the creative requirements of the work of employees are met, then they tend to be satisfied (Shalley, Gilson & Blum, 2000). At a more pragmatic level, career development (without promotion) is the most important thing for young and old employees, so it is related to job satisfaction for equal opportunities. So, there will be job satisfaction if career development is an equal opportunity for young and old employees.
2. **Salary;** Employees see salary as a reflection of how management views their contribution to the company. Additional benefits are also important but not very influential. So the most important thing in meeting employee job satisfaction is the salary value provided by the company. But the benefits will

increase satisfaction if given commensurate with the employee's performance.

3. **Promotion opportunities;** Promotion has a number of different forms and various forms of appreciation. For example, individuals who are promoted on the basis of seniority (length of work) often experience job satisfaction, but not as much as people who are promoted on the basis of performance. In addition, promotions with a 10 percent salary increase are basically not as satisfying as a 20 percent salary increase. This difference helps explain why executive promotions may be more satisfying than promotions that occur at the lower levels of the organization.
4. **Supervision;** Supervision (supervision) is another important source of job satisfaction. For now it can be said that there are two dimensions of supervision style that affect job satisfaction. The first is employee centered, measured by the degree to which supervisors use personal interest and care for employees. It is generally manifested in ways such as examining how well employees work, providing advice and assistance to individuals, and communicating with colleagues personally and in work contexts. Another dimension is participation or influence, as illustrated by managers that allow people to participate in making decisions that affect their work. In many cases, this method leads to higher job satisfaction.
5. **Co-workers/Workmates;** The natural attitude of the group or team work will affect job satisfaction. In general, co-workers or cooperative team members are the simplest source of job satisfaction for individual employees. Working groups, especially "strong" teams, act as a source of support, comfort, advice and assistance to individual members. Recent research indicates that groups that require interdependence among members in completing work will have higher job

satisfaction. (Vegt, Emans & Vliert, 2001).

The performance

Performance is often interpreted as the achievement of the task, where the term achievement of the task itself comes from the thought of the activities needed by workers (Lindholm, 2000). Christine et al. (2010) performance is the achievement of an outcome that is characterized by the expertise of an individual or group's tasks on the basis of predetermined objectives. Performance is the result or the final level of overall success of a person during a certain period in carrying out the task compared to various possibilities, such as work standards, targets or targets, or predetermined criteria and agreed upon together (Rivai and Basri, 2005). In Faustino Cardoso Gomes (2003), a type of performance criteria that measures the work performance of workers based on specific behavioral descriptions, including: Quantity of Work, Quality of Work, Job Knowledge, Creativeness, Corporation, Dependability, Initiative, and Personal Qualities. This type of performance criterion has long been used in organizations, both in the public and private sectors. The dimensions of the criteria type are explained as follows:

1. Quantity of Work, the amount of work done in a specified period.
2. Quality of Work, Quality of work achieved based on the conditions of suitability and readiness.
3. Job Knowledge, knowledge of the job and its skills.
4. Creativeness, the authenticity of ideas - ideas raised and actions - actions to solve problems that arise.
5. Cooperation, the willingness to cooperate with others (fellow members of the organization).
6. Dependability, awareness of trustworthiness (commitment) in the presence and completion of work.
7. Initiative, the enthusiasm to carry out new tasks and to enlarge their responsibilities.

8. Personal Qualities, concerning personality, leadership, hospitality and personal integrity.

Therefore based on the consideration of the results of the previous research, the researcher wants to test the same variable to answer the phenomenon of employee performance in the TelkomselRTPO Work

Unit in Sumatra Area where the specified target is not achieved for two consecutive years, ie from 2017 to 2018. So in the writing of the study with the title "The Effect of Emotional Exhaustion and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance in Telkomsel RTPO Work Unit in Sumatra Area" can be presented in the conceptual framework as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

Based on the conceptual framework of this research, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

H₁: Emotional Exhaustion has a significant negative effect on Job Satisfaction of employees in the Sumatra Area Telkomsel RTPO Work Unit

H₂: Job Satisfaction has a significant positive effect on employee performance in the Sumatra Area Telkomsel RTPO Work Unit

H₃: Emotional Exhaustion and Job Satisfaction have a significant influence on the performance of employees in the Sumatra Area Telkomsel RTPO Work Unit

RESEARCH METHOD

The method used in this study is correlational. Correlational research is research that aims to detect the extent to which variations in a factor are related to variations in one or more other factors based on the correlation coefficient (Masyhuri and Zainuddin, 2008). The population in this study was 84 employees in the Sumatra

Area Telkomsel RTPO Work Unit. Determination of this population is based on the background of the research which focuses on measuring emotional exhaustion, job satisfaction, and performance where employees in the RTPO Work Unit as one of the frontline in achieving management targets have a reflection of emotional Exhaustion and job satisfaction at the company and this can also be a input for the managerial to see the conditions of work performance of its employees. Sampling in this study was conducted with a total sampling technique used with the consideration that the total population is below 200 people, namely as many as 84 respondents.

Data in this study will be collected through primary data and secondary data. To get the data to be processed, the data collection techniques used by the author in this study are (1) Field research / field research, namely interviews, preliminary studies to find research problems, and questionnaires, using a question format that uses a scale ; (2) Library studies / library

research, namely studies conducted by studying compulsory books (textbooks), supplementary or reference books, magazines, journals, official reports from companies. In this study, the measurement scale used is a Likert scale (Sugiyono, 2011)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this study the independent variables observed were Emotional Exhaustion (X_1) and Job Satisfaction (X_2) which also acted as intervening variables while the observed dependent variables were employee performance of Telkomsel's RTPO Work Unit in the Sumatra Area (Y).

Table 1. Reliability test results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Item
Emotional Exhaustion (X_1)	0.814	24
Job Satisfaction (X_2)	0.908	16
Performances (Y)	0.963	29

Source: Research data processed 2019

From the results of the questionnaire reliability test on all variables obtained Cronbach Alpha values greater than 0.212. This shows that each item of the questionnaire proved to be reliable for use in the study.

Normality Test Results

Normality testing in this study aims to determine whether in the regression model, residual values are normally distributed or not. A good regression model is a model that has a residual value that meets the normality assumption, namely the $\text{Sig.} > \alpha$ (0.05). To test the normality in this study using the Kolmogorov Smirnov Test approach. The results of the normality test using the Kolmogorov Smirnov Test approach can be seen in Table 2.

Tabel 2. One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		80
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	11.91535229
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.085
	Positive	.085
	Negative	-.059
Test Statistic		.085
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}

Source: Research data processed 2019

The normality test results revealed that the Asymp.Sig (2-tailed) value was 0.200. This value is greater than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. Then it can be concluded that the residual value is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test is used to find out whether in the regression model there is a linear relationship between the independent variables. Multicollinearity test results can be seen in Table 3 as follows:

Tabel 3. One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized		Standardized		Co-linearity Statistics		
		Coefficients		Coefficients				
			Std.					
Model		B	Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	32.318	10.131		3.190	.002		
	Emotional Exhaustion (X_1)	.985	.111	.758	8.869	.000	.765	1.308
	Work Satisfaction (X_2)	-.015	.169	-.007	-.087	.931	.765	1.308

a. Dependent Variable: PERFORMANCE(Y)

Source: Research data processed 2019

The multicollinearity test results obtained Tolerance value of 0.765 each. These results are greater than 0.10, then each VIF value is 1,308. The result is

smaller than 10, so in the regression model there is no linear relationship between the independent variables (no multicollinearity).

R-square Model Test (R²)

Testing the coefficient of determination is done to find out how much the contribution or contribution of the independent variable Emotional Exhaustion and Job Satisfaction simultaneously. The results of the coefficient of determination test can be seen in Table 4 as follows:

Table 4. R-square Model Test Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.755 ^a	.570	.558	12.069

Source: Research data processed 2019

The coefficient of determination test results obtained the value of the coefficient of

determination (R square) of 0.570, which means that 57% of the variables Emotional Exhaustion and Job Satisfaction influence on Performance, and the remaining 43% is explained by other variables not examined in this study.

F Test (Simultaneous)

To determine the effect of Emotional Exhaustion, and Job Satisfaction on Performance on the employees of the Telkomsel RTPO unit in the Sumatra area simultaneously, a hypothesis test was conducted simultaneously (FTest). The results of simultaneous hypothesis testing (F Test) can be seen in Table 5 below:

Table 5. F Test Results (Simultaneous) ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14841.476	2	7420.738	50.944	.000 ^b
	Residual	11216.074	77	145.663		
	Total	26057.550	79			

Source: Research data processed 2019

The results of simultaneous hypothesis testing (Test F) obtained a value of 50.944 with (N₁) of 3.11. It can be concluded > (50,944 > 3,11) and the significance value is smaller than the significant level $\alpha = 0.05$ (0,000 < 0.05). Thus, the third hypothesis is accepted which states that Emotional Exhaustion and Job Satisfaction have a significant and simultaneous effect on Performance.

T test (partial)

T test is one of the research hypothesis tests in simple linear regression analysis and multiple linear regression analysis. T test aims to determine whether the independent variable or independent variable partially (individually) affect the dependent variable or the dependent variable (Y).

Direct Effect Test

Test Results Direct Effect on the variable Emotional Exhaustion (X₁) on Job Satisfaction (X₂) can be seen in Table 6

Table 6. Test Results of Direct Effect (X₁ to X₂) Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	-5.180	7.016		-.738	.462
	Emotional Exhaustion (X ₁)	.708	.077	.713	9.208	.000

a. Dependent Variable: x2

Source: Research data processed 2019

It is known that the direct effect of Emotional Exhaustion (X₁) on Job Satisfaction (X₂) shows that the direct effect of X₁ on X₂ is 0.713 with a significant value of 0.000. Thus, X₁ has a positive effect on X₂ and is significant (significant 0.000 < 0.05). Test Results Direct Effect on the variables Emotional Exhaustion (X₁) and Job Satisfaction (X₂) on Performance (Y) can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7. Direct Effect Test Results (X₁ and X₂ to Y)

Model		Coefficients ^a		Beta	t	Sig.
		Unstandardized				
		Coefficients				
1	(Constant)	66.950	10.685		6.266	.000
	Emotional Exhaustion (X ₁)	.261	.166	.203	1.567	.121
	Job Satisfaction (X ₂)	.530	.168	.411	3.164	.002

a. Dependent Variable: y

Source: Research data processed 2019

It is known that in testing the direct effect of Emotional Exhaustion (X₁) and Job Satisfaction (X₂) on Performance (Y) obtained results:

1. The direct effect of X₁ on Y is 0.203 with a significant value of 0.121. Thus, X₁ has a positive effect on Y but is not significant (significant 0.121 > 0.05).
2. The direct effect of X₂ on Y is 0.411 with a significant value of 0.002. Thus, X₂ has a positive effect on Y and is significant (significant 0.002 < 0.05).

Indirect Effect Test

Figure 2. Path Analysis

From the picture above, it is known that the indirect effect of Emotional Exhaustion (X₁) on Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (X₂) can be calculated as follows:

1. Direct Effect of X₁ on X₂ = 0.713
2. Direct Effect of X₂ on Y = 0.411
3. The indirect effect of X₁ on Y through X₂ = 0.713 x 0.411 = 0.293

Based on the results of the t test, it can be seen that Emotional Exhaustion (X₁) has a significant direct effect on Job Satisfaction (X₂) of 0.713. Furthermore, it

can also be seen that Job Satisfaction (X₂) has a significant direct effect on Performance (Y) of 0.411. The indirect effect of Emotional Exhaustion (X₁) through Job Satisfaction (X₂) on Performance (Y) is 0.293. The variable Emotional Exhaustion (X₁) does not directly affect on Performance (Y), but Emotional Exhaustion (X₁) significantly influences Job Satisfaction (X₂), where Job Satisfaction (X₂) significantly influence Performance (Y). In other words Emotional Exhaustion (X₁) affects Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (X₂). Emotional Exhaustion that

is felt by employees in the Telkomsel RTPO Work Unit of Sumatra Area affects performance, including the work environment faced is quite draining and has a high work risk. This has indeed become part of the RTPO Work Unit. Therefore, the things that encourage employees to behave better at work need to be considered to maximize the effectiveness of employee work, such as monetary compensation (overtime allowances and risk allowances) and also non-monetary ones (career development and training).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results and discussion of the study entitled "The Effect of Emotional Exhaustion and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance in the Telkomsel RTPO Work Unit in Sumatra Area" which has been tested based on a questionnaire that has been completed by each Telkomsel RTPO unit employee in the Sumatra Area, it can be concluded that :

1. Emotional Exhaustion has a direct significant effect on the Job Satisfaction of Telkomsel RTPO Work Unit in Sumatra Area employees.
2. Job Satisfaction has a significant direct effect on the performance of Telkomsel RTPO Work Unit in Sumatra Area employees.
3. Emotional Exhaustion indirectly and significantly affects Performance through Job Satisfaction of Telkomsel RTPO Work Unit in Sumatra Area employees.

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